

MAH JOURNAL

DEFENCE SERVICES MEDICAL RESEARCH CENTRE

ISSN 2522-6266

Volume 12, No. 2

August, 2025

MYANMAR ARMY HEALTH JOURNAL

**Official Journal of
Defence Services Medical Research Centre**

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Official Journal of Defence Services Medical Research Centre

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MYANMAR ARMY HEALTH JOURNAL

Official Journal of Defence Services Medical Research Centre

Volume 12, No. 2

August, 2025

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MYANMAR ARMY HEALTH JOURNAL

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Myanmar Army Health Journal is a professional medical and health science research journal to address the following aims and objectives:

1. To equip the members of medical corps by disseminating impartial biomedical information discovered nationally and internationally up to date in order to make soldiers healthy and fit to fight.
2. To inspire the military healthcare professionals to conduct researches relevant to the welfare and benefits of the soldiers and family members of Tatmadaw and the people of the country.
3. To support creating research culture and environment among and inclusive of experienced and inexperienced healthcare personnel.
4. To serve as a suitable ground and to provide opportunities to nurture research article writing skills and to archive the research works of military medical scientists.

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Association between Vitamin-K Epoxide Reductase Complex Subunit 1 (VKORC1) Polymorphism and Dosage of Warfarin in Myanmar Patients with Atrial Fibrillation or Mechanical Heart Valve

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Abstract

Background: Warfarin is a widely prescribed oral anticoagulant with a narrow therapeutic index and substantial inter-individual variability in dose requirements. Genetic factors, particularly polymorphisms in the *vitamin K epoxide reductase complex subunit 1 (VKORC1)* gene, play a major role in this variability. Data on pharmacogenomic determinants of warfarin dosing in Myanmar remain scarce.

Objective: To evaluate the distribution of *VKORC1 -1639G>A* polymorphisms and their impact on warfarin dose requirements among patients in Myanmar.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 patients on long-term warfarin therapy. Demographic data, daily maintenance dose, and stable international normalized ratio (INR) values were collected. Genotyping of *VKORC1 -1639G>A* was performed using validated methods, and associations between genotype and mean daily warfarin dose were analyzed.

Results: The study population was predominantly Bamar ethnicity (94%). Warfarin dose requirements ranged from 1.0 to 8.33 mg/day, with a mean of 3.68 ± 1.67 mg/day. Most patients (68%) required <5 mg/day. Genotype distribution was 41% AA, 51% AG, and 8% GG, with allele frequencies of 66.5% (A) and 33.5% (G), consistent with Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium. Mean warfarin dose differed significantly by genotype ($p < 0.001$): AA carriers required the lowest doses (2.53 ± 0.86 mg/day), AG carriers intermediate doses (4.24 ± 1.60 mg/day), and GG carriers the highest doses (5.95 ± 0.99 mg/day). Age and BMI showed no significant association.

Conclusion: This study demonstrates that the *VKORC1 -1639G>A* polymorphism significantly influences warfarin dose requirements in the Myanmar population, with genotype distribution resembling other Southeast Asian cohorts. The predominance of low-dose–associated alleles highlights the need for genotype-guided dosing strategies to optimize anticoagulation therapy and minimize bleeding risk. Incorporation of pharmacogenomic data into clinical practice may improve the safety and efficacy of warfarin therapy in Myanmar.

Keywords: International normalized ratio (INR), Myanmar patients, Vitamin K epoxide reductase complex subunit 1 (VKORC1), *VKORC1 -1639G>A* polymorphisms, Warfarin

1. Introduction

Genetic variation plays a critical role in determining interindividual differences in drug response through its impact on pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. Advances in pharmacogenomics have demonstrated that polymorphisms in genes encoding drug-metabolizing enzymes, receptors, and transporters contribute significantly to variability in drug disposition, efficacy, and adverse reactions.¹ Variants affecting metabolism or transport alter drug pharmacokinetics, while single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in drug target genes influence pharmacodynamics.²

Despite widespread use, many prescribed medications achieve therapeutic efficacy in only ~60% of patients, and adverse drug reactions (ADRs) remain a major clinical concern.³ Classic examples of genotype–ADR associations include haemolytic anaemia in glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase–deficient patients following antimalarials or sulphonamides, prolonged neuromuscular blockade from suxamethonium in cholinesterase deficiency, and thiopurine toxicity in patients lacking thiopurine S-methyltransferase. Improved understanding of genetic determinants of drug response is essential for elucidating underlying mechanisms and guiding individualized treatment strategies.

Warfarin, a widely used oral anticoagulant, is prescribed for prevention and treatment of thromboembolic disorders including atrial fibrillation, prosthetic heart valves, deep vein thrombosis, and pulmonary embolism.⁴ Its therapeutic effect is monitored via the international normalized ratio (INR), with a target range of 2.0–3.0.⁵ Warfarin has nearly complete oral bioavailability and predictable absorption, but exhibits substantial interindividual variability in dose requirements.⁶ It acts by inhibiting the vitamin K epoxide reductase complex subunit 1 (VKORC1), thereby reducing activation of vitamin K–dependent coagulation factors II, VII, IX, and X.⁷ Administered as a racemic mixture, S-warfarin—metabolized primarily by CYP2C9—is more potent than R-warfarin, which is metabolized by CYP1A1, CYP1A2, and CYP3A4.

Warfarin's narrow therapeutic index demands precise dosing: subtherapeutic INR values increase thrombosis risk, whereas supratherapeutic values heighten bleeding risk.⁸ Clinical variables such as age, body mass index, diet, ethnicity, and drug interactions explain only 15–20% of dose variability.^{9,10} Genetic polymorphisms, particularly in CYP2C9 and VKORC1, account for 30–50% of this variability.¹¹ CYP2C92 and CYP2C93 alleles markedly reduce S-warfarin metabolism, lowering clearance and necessitating reduced doses.¹² The VKORC1 –1639G>A promoter variant decreases VKORC1 expression, increasing warfarin sensitivity.⁹

Ethnic variation in VKORC1 genotype distribution significantly influences dose requirements. The AA genotype predominates in East and Southeast Asians—who generally require lower doses—while African Americans more frequently carry the GG genotype and require higher.^{13,14} Recognizing these genetic effects, the Clinical Pharmacogenetics Implementation Consortium (CPIC) recommends genotype-guided warfarin dosing when genetic data are available.¹⁵

In Myanmar, warfarin is commonly prescribed for atrial fibrillation and mechanical heart valves, but dosing remains guided primarily by INR monitoring. This study investigates the frequency of VKORC1 –1639G>A polymorphism in Myanmar patients receiving warfarin and evaluates its impact on dose requirements. Findings may establish baseline pharmacogenetic data for this population and support the adoption of genotype-guided dosing to optimize safety and efficacy.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Design and Setting

A hospital-based, cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted from January 2017 to November 2019 at the Outpatient Departments of Cardiac Surgery and Cardiac Medicine, No. (1) Defence Services General Hospital (1000-bedded), Mingalardon, Yangon, Myanmar. INR measurement was performed at the hospital's Clinical Investigation Laboratory, and genotyping was carried out at the Immunology Research Division, Department of Medical Research, Yangon, Myanmar.

2.2. Study Population

Eligible participants (n=100) were adults (18–75 years) with atrial fibrillation or mechanical heart valves, receiving warfarin therapy, and maintaining a stable international normalized ratio (INR) between 2.0 and 3.0 over the last three consecutive visits. Seriously ill patients were excluded.

2.3. Recruitment and Ethical Considerations

Eligible patients were recruited consecutively during routine clinic visits. Written informed consent was obtained after explaining study objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Each participant was assigned a coded identifier to ensure confidentiality. The study was approved by the ethics review committee of Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

2.4. Data Collection

Demographic data (age, sex, body mass index), clinical history, medication use, warfarin dose, and INR values for the preceding three visits were recorded using a structured proforma.

2.5. Blood Sample Collection and Processing

Venous blood (5 mL) was collected aseptically:

- **Genotyping:** 3 mL in EDTA tubes, stored at -80°C until DNA extraction.
- **INR measurement:** 2 mL in sodium citrate tubes, processed immediately.

2.6. Genotyping of VKORC1 (–1639G>A)

Genomic DNA was extracted using the Genomic DNA Blood Mini Kit (Geneaid™, Taiwan) according to manufacturer instructions. VKORC1 genotypes were determined by polymerase chain reaction–restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR–RFLP).

PCR amplification:

- **Primers:**
Forward: 5'-GCCAGCAGGAGAGGGAAATA-3'
Reverse: 5'-AGTTTGGACTACAGGTGCCT-3' (Macrogen Co., Korea).
- Reaction mix (25 μL): 2 μL DNA template, 0.5 μL each primer (100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), 2.5 μL 10 \times PCR buffer with Mg^{2+} , 2 μL dNTPs (2.5 mmol/L), 0.25 μL Taq polymerase, and nuclease-free water.
- Cycling: initial denaturation (95°C , 5 min); 35 cycles of denaturation (94°C , 30 s), annealing (60°C , 30 s), extension (72°C , 45 s); final extension (72°C , 7 min).

Restriction digestion and electrophoresis: PCR products (8 μL) were digested with MspI at 37°C overnight and separated on 2.5% agarose gels stained with ethidium bromide. Bands were visualized under UV light:

- GG: 168 bp + 122 bp

- AG: 290 bp + 168 bp + 122 bp
- AA: 290 bp (undigested).

2.7. INR Measurement

INR values were determined using the Hamclot Duo Plus coagulation analyzer (Human GmbH, Germany) with Haemostat Thromboplastin-SI reagent, following standard operating procedures.

2.8. Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0 (IBM Corp., USA). Genotype and allele frequencies were calculated by direct counting. Associations between variables and warfarin dose were tested using Pearson's correlation. A p -value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Baseline Characteristics of the Study Population

A total of 100 patients receiving warfarin therapy were enrolled. The mean age was 50.58 ± 12.03 years (range 18–75 years), with a nearly equal sex distribution (49 males, 51 females). The mean body mass index (BMI) was 21.65 ± 4.01 kg/m². The majority of participants (58%) were being treated for mechanical heart valve replacements, while 15% had atrial fibrillation and 27% had more than one disease. (Table-1)

The mean daily warfarin dose required to achieve therapeutic anticoagulation (INR 2.0–3.0) was 3.68 ± 1.67 mg/day. (Table-2) The most common result was 5 mg per day for 16 patients followed by 2 mg per day for 15 patients and 2.5 mg per day and 3 mg per day for 14 patients each. The mean INR across the last three consecutive visits was 2.46 ± 0.39 , confirming stable anticoagulation status. (Figure-1)

3.2. VKORC1 Genotype Distribution

Genotyping of VKORC1 (–1639G>A) revealed three distinct genotypes: GG (wild-type), AG (heterozygous), and AA (homozygous mutant). (Table-3)(Figure 2 and 3) The distribution was as follows:

- GG: 8% (n = 8)
- AG: 51% (n = 51)
- AA: 41% (n = 41)

The observed genotype frequencies were consistent with Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium ($p > 0.05$). Allele frequencies were 66.5% for the A allele and 33.5% for the G allele.

3.3. Association Between Genotypes and Warfarin Dose

The mean daily warfarin dose differed significantly across the three VKORC1 genotypes (ANOVA, $p < 0.001$) as in Figure 4.

- **GG genotype:** 5.95 ± 0.99 mg/day
- **AG genotype:** 4.24 ± 1.60 mg/day
- **AA genotype:** 2.53 ± 0.86 mg/day

Post hoc analysis (Tukey HSD) demonstrated that each genotype group differed significantly from the others ($p < 0.05$ for all pairwise comparisons). Thus, carriers of the A allele required substantially lower doses of warfarin compared to G allele carriers, with AA homozygotes requiring the least. (Table-4)

3.4. Correlation Between Warfarin Dose and Clinical Variables

Pearson's correlation analysis revealed no significant correlation between warfarin dose and age ($p = 0.52$) or BMI ($p = 0.33$). The only significant determinant of warfarin dose requirement was VKORC1 genotype ($p < 0.001$). (Table-5)

3.5. Summary of Findings

1. The VKORC1 (-1639G>A) polymorphism was present at a high frequency in the study population, with 66.5% carrying at least one A allele.
2. A clear gene-dose relationship was observed: patients with GG genotype required the highest warfarin doses, AG genotypes required intermediate doses, and AA genotypes required the lowest doses.
3. Other demographic and clinical factors (age and BMI) did not significantly influence warfarin dose requirements in this cohort.

4. Discussion

Warfarin remains the cornerstone oral anticoagulant for the prevention and treatment of thromboembolic events in diverse clinical contexts, including atrial fibrillation, mechanical heart valve replacement, venous thromboembolism, and stroke prevention.⁴ Despite its established efficacy, warfarin therapy poses substantial clinical challenges due to its narrow therapeutic index and significant inter-individual variability in dose requirements. Both sub-therapeutic and supra-therapeutic anticoagulation carry serious risks, the former predisposing to thromboembolism and the latter to hemorrhage.¹⁶ Optimizing initial and maintenance dosing is therefore critical but often difficult for clinicians, as dose requirements are influenced by a combination of genetic, demographic, physiological, and environmental factors.¹⁷

One of the most important determinants of warfarin sensitivity is genetic variation, particularly polymorphisms in the **vitamin K epoxide reductase complex subunit 1 (VKORC1)** gene. Populations in East and Southeast Asia demonstrate particularly high prevalence of VKORC1 variants, with over 90% carrying the low-dose-associated alleles.¹⁸ This is a striking contrast to other regions, such as South Asia, Europe, and Africa, where the distribution of variant and non-variant alleles is more balanced. The present study contributes novel data on the Myanmar population, a group for which pharmacogenomic information on warfarin response has been scarce.

The study population consisted of 100 patients on long-term warfarin therapy, predominantly of Bamar ethnicity (94%). Warfarin doses in these patients ranged widely from 1.0 to 8.33 mg/day, with a mean of 3.68 ± 1.67 mg/day among those maintaining stable INR. Notably, 68% of patients required less than 5 mg/day, consistent with findings from other East and Southeast Asian cohorts.¹⁹ The most common daily doses were 5 mg (16%), 2 mg (15%), and 2.5–3 mg (14% each), underscoring the high frequency of low-dose requirements.

Age and BMI showed no significant correlation, in line with studies in Caucasian and Asian cohorts.^{20,21} Contrasting findings in another study suggest that BMI is an important clinical factor in assessing and managing warfarin therapy.²²

A central finding of this study is the high prevalence of the VKORC1 -1639G>A polymorphism. Genotype distribution was 41% AA, 51% AG, and only 8% GG, with allele frequencies of 66.5% for A and 33.5% for G. This distribution conforms to Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and mirrors patterns seen in other East and Southeast Asian populations, including Thai cohorts.²³ By comparison, A allele frequencies are markedly lower in Caucasians (~40%), Hispanics (~44%), Ashkenazi Jews (~47%), and African-Americans

(~11%), where G allele predominance results in higher average dose requirements.¹⁹ The similarity between Myanmar and Thai populations highlights regional genetic homogeneity within mainland Southeast Asia.

Consistent with prior pharmacogenomic studies, warfarin dose requirements in this cohort correlated strongly with VKORC1 genotype. Patients with the AA genotype required the lowest mean daily dose (2.53 ± 0.86 mg/day), whereas AG carriers required intermediate doses (4.24 ± 1.60 mg/day), and GG homozygotes required the highest (5.95 ± 0.99 mg/day). These differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and in close agreement with data from European and Asian studies, where patients carrying the VKORC1 -1639 GA or AA genotypes (A allele carriers) required significantly lower warfarin doses compared to GG carriers, with the weighted mean difference in dosage ranging from 26% to 50% lower.^{23,24}

Mechanistically, the -1639G>A polymorphism alters the promoter activity of the VKORC1 gene, reducing expression of the vitamin K epoxide reductase enzyme. The resulting diminished enzymatic activity heightens sensitivity to warfarin, thereby lowering dose requirements.²⁵ This effect is most pronounced in homozygous AA individuals.

The findings of this study reinforce the importance of integrating pharmacogenomic information into warfarin therapy in Myanmar. The predominance of low-dose-associated VKORC1 variants suggests that empiric dosing strategies derived from Western populations may risk over-anticoagulation and bleeding complications in Myanmar patients. Incorporating genotype-guided algorithms into routine practice could improve safety and shorten the time to achieve stable INR. Indeed, international guidelines increasingly recommend the use of genetic information—specifically VKORC1 and CYP2C9 genotypes—when available, to guide initial dosing.

Although CYP2C9 polymorphisms were not evaluated in this study, their prevalence in neighboring Southeast Asian populations is reported to be relatively low (<6%), suggesting a smaller contribution to dose variability compared with VKORC1.¹⁸ Nonetheless, future studies incorporating both genetic and non-genetic determinants—including diet, drug interactions, and herbal supplement use—are warranted to build comprehensive dosing models tailored for Myanmar.

5. Strengths and Limitations

This is the first study to report VKORC1 genotype distribution and its relationship with warfarin dose in the Myanmar population. The findings are robust, with adequate sample size and genotyping validation under Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. The cohort was overwhelmingly of Bamar ethnicity, limiting generalizability to other Myanmar ethnic groups. Genetic contributions from CYP2C9 and other loci were not assessed, and clinical outcomes such as bleeding or thromboembolic events were not examined. Moreover, lifestyle and dietary influences were not systematically quantified. Addressing these gaps will be essential for developing population-specific dosing guidelines.

6. Conclusion

In summary, this study demonstrates that VKORC1 -1639G>A polymorphisms exert a significant influence on warfarin dose requirements among Myanmar patients, with genotype distributions closely resembling those of other Southeast Asian populations. The predominance of low-dose-associated alleles underscores the need for tailored dosing strategies in Myanmar, emphasizing the role of pharmacogenetics in guiding safe and effective anticoagulation therapy. These results support broader implementation of

personalized medicine approaches and pave the way for larger, multi-ethnic studies in Myanmar.

7. Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express our gratitude to specialist officers and staffs from Cardiac Medical Unit of No(1) Defence Services General Hospital (1000-bedded), Yangon, Myanmar and Dr. Aye Aye Lwin, Deputy Director, Immunology Research Division, DMR, Yangon, for her guidance, supports and for providing the research facilities for genotyping of the patients.

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Table (1) Demographic and clinical data of study population (n=100)

Clinical characteristics	Value
Age (years) (Mean ±SD)	50.58±12.03
Sex (% population)	
Male	49
Female	51
BMI (kg/m ²) (Mean ±SD)	21.65±4.01
Male BMI (kg/m ²) (Mean ±SD)	21.52±4.12
Female BMI(kg/m ²) (Mean ±SD)	21.77±3.93
BMI Class (% population)	
Obese (>30)	5
Overweight (25-29.9)	19
Normal Weight (18.5-24.9)	50
Underweight (<18)	26
Disease (% population)	
AF	15
MHV	58
More than one disease or combined AF+MHV	27

Table (2) Description of stable warfarin dose in stable INR in study population

Variable	n	Minimum Dose(mg/day)	Maximum Dose(mg/day)	Mean±SD	Mode
Warfarin dose	100	1	8.33	3.68±1.67	5.0

Table (3) Genotype and allele frequency of VKORC1 (-1639G>A) gene polymorphism in study population (n=100)

VKORC1 Gene polymorphism	No.	Percent
Genotype		
AA	41	41%
AG	51	51%
GG	8	8%
Allele		
A	133	66.5%
G	67	33.5%

Table (4) Comparison of mean daily warfarin dose between different VKORC1 genotype groups (Post Hoc analysis of ANOVA) (n=100)

Dependent Variable	Compared group	Mean Difference	p value
Mean daily warfarin dose (mg/day)	AA genotype group vs AG genotype group	1.71	<0.001*
	AA genotype group vs GG genotype group	3.42	<0.001*
	AG genotype group vs GG genotype group	1.70	0.002*

Table (5) Comparison of age, BMI, daily warfarin dose in stable INR among different genotypes of VKORC1 (-1639G>A) polymorphism in study population (n=100)

Parameters	AA Genotype	AG Genotype	GG Genotype	ANOVA	
				F	p value
Age(year)	49.37±12.44	51.22±11.23	46.50±15.32	0.64	0.52
BMI	21.21±3.72	22.20±4.36	21.650±4.01	1.09	0.33
Warfarin dose (mg/day)	2.53±0.86	4.24±1.60	5.95±0.99	32.84	<0.001*

Results were shown in Mean ± SD, *p = <0.05 was significant

Figure (1) Number of patients and daily warfarin dose in stable INR in the study population

Figure (2) Association between daily warfarin dose and VKORC1 genotypes in study population